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ESPAÑÓLES, INDIOS, AFRICANOS Y GITANOS.
EL ALCANCE GLOBAL DEL FANDANGO EN MÚSICA, CANTO Y DANZA

SPANIARDS, INDIANS, AFRICANS AND GYPSIES:
THE GLOBAL REACH OF THE FANDANGO IN MUSIC, SONG, AND
DANCE

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EMERGENCE AND TRANSFORMATIONS OF THE FANDANGO

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Resumen

Habiendo llegado a todas las capas de la sociedad española, el fandango sufrió cambios imprevistos, no solo de estilo y técnica, sino también de estructura musical y hasta en la métrica. El baile voluptuoso, espontáneo y poco estructurado descrito por Casanova, entre otros, fue sometido a reglas, adornado con pasos del baile cortesano, y moldeado de nuevo al modo de la *country-dance* inglesa o *contredance* francesa. Un híbrido bastante improbable del fandango y el minueto, el *minué afandangado*, llegó a destacar fugazmente en la escena musical, mientras que las *seguidillas*, con su estructura típica *copla/estribillo*, influenciaron decididamente los fandangos regionales de los pueblos españoles hasta hoy día. Concluimos con una mirada breve hacia la locura desatada por el fandango en la "recatada" sociedad de Boston en la década de los noventa del siglo XVIII. Así mismo, se presentan ejemplos musicales y una variada selección de textos.

Palabras clave:

Minué afandangado, contradanza, seguidillas

Aparición y Transformaciones en el fandango.

Abstract

As it filtered into every level of Spanish society, the fandango underwent surprising changes not only in style and technique but also musical structure and even meter. The voluptuous, spontaneous and nearly unstructured dance described by Casanova and others was subjected to rules, ornamented with courtly steps and recast in the mold of the English country-dance and French contredanse. An unlikely hybrid of the fandango and minuet, the *minué afandangado*, briefly found favor, while the alternating *copla/estribillo* structure typical of the *seguidillas* durably marked the regional fandangos danced in Spanish villages even today. We end with a glimpse at the little-known fandango fever that seized the straight-laced town of Boston in the 1790s. Musical examples and a wide-ranging selection of texts are included.

Key Words:

Minué afandangado, contredanse, seguidillas

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Between its appearance at the turn of the eighteenth century and its decadence toward the mid-nineteenth, the fandango abandoned its original "obscene" aspect, disguising itself in the cloak of several other dances. Relying on dance manuals, correspondence, travel diaries and musical sources, I hope to provide a few clear answers to the most basic question: What did the fandango really look like during the course of these transformations? From time to time, in search of supporting evidence, we will abandon the ballroom for the professional stage, the fairground or the public square.

First, we should put certain legends into perspective, beginning with the fandango's reputation as a "forbidden" dance. Casanova leads us to believe that it was banned by the Spanish Inquisition and permitted once again by the Conde de Aranda, head of the Council of Castile. In fact the "ban" most likely was introduced by the Marqués de Esquilache two years before Casanova's arrival. Today this statesman's economic reforms would be considered "austerity measures." Until a study clarifies the question, we may assume that costly balls and wasteful banquets were the main target, and that the fandango was merely an indirect victim, and only for a short time.

Another persistent anecdote is the "trial" of the fandango. Threatened by condemnation by the Pope (presumably Clement XIII, known for his prudishness), the offensive dance was performed before a council of cardinals. Discovering that they could not resist stamping and swaying from side to side, they decided that such a naturally infectious dance must be

harmless. Until evidence is presented to the contrary, this episode should be considered an amusing fabrication.

However, if the fandango had been perfectly chaste it never would have inspired such legends. How exactly did this dance appear “lascivious” in its earliest phase?

The fandango was immortalized by several writers for its sensuality and provocative allure. Three sources stand out: a letter of 1712, in Latin, by Manuel Martí, a clergyman of Alicante passing through Cádiz; a 1764 letter by Beaumarchais, author of the “Figaro” comedies; and, finally, Casanova’s account of a public ball in Madrid during his travels of 1767-68. These narratives tend to be more evocative than technical, yet they provide a surprising amount of concrete information. All three sources pose problems. Casanova and Beaumarchais intended to entertain and even titillate their readers. Their accounts are therefore subject to circumspection. As for Martí, his letter has long been cited in contradictory translations that did not inspire confidence.

A quite recent study by José Francisco Ortega Castejón answers many questions but raises a new controversy: Martí never once mentions the word “fandango”! Nevertheless, his letter coincides exactly with the fandango’s spread across Andalucía, a fact that cannot be underestimated. Taking into account Ortega’s paper and a fresh approach to the original Latin (for which I am indebted to the French Latinist Tanguy Neveu), let us essay a new rendering of the familiar passage in simple English:

Now I ask you to consider the licentiousness of ancient customs and censure them, while praising the modesty of our own customs. You have already heard of this dance of Cádiz, which has always been known for its obscenity. Nowadays you would see this very dance performed in every public square and in every room of every home in this town. Applauded beyond belief by everyone standing about, it is performed and appreciated not only by dark-skinned folk and people of low station, but also by respectable ladies of noble birth.

This is how it is danced. A man and a woman dance together, sometimes one couple, sometimes more. They move to the music, arousing lust in every way imaginable: by curving their arms in extremely soft gestures, moving their buttocks again and again, twitching their thighs, and provoking each other suggestively. They engage in all kinds of unbridled sexual mimicry with the greatest skill and fervor. You can see the man thrust his hips while the woman moans and writhes. She does this with such grace and elegance that the trembling hindquarters of the maiden Photis, as described by Apuleius, would seem graceless and crude by comparison. In short, this is exactly how one might imagine Hercules and Omphale dancing together.

themselves, seized with the fury of the satyric dance, are drawn into this representation of desire, and they sway gently and nod their heads.

Numerous details remain open to interpretation. The words usually translated as “voluptuous undulations” literally indicate an extremely soft bending of the “members,” which might imply the arms or perhaps the whole body (a “harmonious convulsion” of the entire body was later observed by the Italian traveler Giuseppe Barretti). The good father’s eyes were drawn to the hips and hindquarters, particularly those of the woman. The movement of the buttocks, sometimes rendered as “swaying,” does not necessarily imply motion from side to side; the pelvic thrusts of the man logically should be forward and back, and yet a certain ambiguity remains, as the term in question was also used for a dog wagging its tail. Martí does not in any way imply that the couple performed identical steps as La Meri claimed in the 1940s. He mentions moaning on the part of the woman, one of the details formerly omitted for reasons of decency, while the “stamping” found in some translations appears in fact to be some kind of throbbing or twitching movement originating in the thighs. Martí makes no mention of castanets or finger-snapping, but the word for “applause” just might suggest rhythmic *palmas*. The “Gypsy women” or “black women” found in some translations are in fact *Aethiopes*, which indicates dark-skinned people, perhaps African, perhaps gypsies, but not exclusively of the female gender. The people found alongside these “Ethiopians,” described as *obscuros*, were not necessarily dark-skinned but merely common or vulgar.

For foreigners like Casanova and Beaumarchais about a half-century later, the fandango was a dance of voluptuous poses. The words “posture,” “gesture” and “pantomime” crop up regularly in their accounts. Casanova saw it as an erotic spectacle in which the man expressed desire and ecstasy and the woman, consent and sexual contentment. It provoked confusion and frenzy among dancers and spectators alike. Beaumarchais recalled the woman taking her place on the dance floor with her gaze cast modestly down, then extending her arms sensuously and snapping her fingers in a mocking, defiant way, as if to say, “I’ll never give in to you.” This contrasts with Casanova’s impression of male conquest and female submission. According to Beaumarchais, it was common for the man to bow out of the dance from fatigue, and his place would be taken by another, and then another. A similar custom was observed by the Englishman Richard Twiss in Portugal, except when exhaustion overcame one or both partners a new couple would take their place.

Beaumarchais mentions an advancing and retreating motif. The man is described as “turning” his partner, sometimes rendered in English as “spinning.” It is more likely that the two partners merely changed places and turned about to face each other with one or several revolutions.

found in Pablo Minguet's *Arte de danzar a la francesa* and *Breve Tratado de los pasos de danzar a la española*, which describe no fewer than forty-seven different Spanish steps in current use in the fandango as well as the seguidillas. Many of these involve vigorous jumping, and, in particular, kicking: a forward kick (*puntapié arriba*), a backward kick (*coz arriba*) and combinations of the two (*floreo*, *cargado* and others). Similar kicks are still found in several regional fandangos. Minguet's text is an expansion of a much earlier treatise by Juan de Esquivel Navarro, *Discursos sobre el arte del dançado*, which dealt with a school of court dance practiced under the Habsbourgs and theoretically extinct. Yet he continued reprinting it as late as the 1760s, always mentioning the fandango and seguidillas.

Minguet even states that *French* steps can be introduced, the first of many indications that the fandango absorbed foreign elements very freely. He also offers a hint to the use of the arms. The cover illustration of the 1764 edition of his *Breve tratado* was in fact recycled from *Arte de danzar a la francesa*, where it illustrated a couple performing a minuet (see Figure 1). The quaint image is hardly voluptuous, but it would suggest that the level of the arms, nearly shoulder-height, was just as appropriate for the fandango and seguidillas as it was for the minuet.

FIGURAS PARA DARSE LAS DOS MANOS.

Figure 1

heel and the *punta* (either the toe or the ball of the foot) were struck on the floor and that *taconeo* sequences were extremely varied and precise, attracting the eye even more than the gestures of the arms. Bartholomé Ferriol y Boxeraus avoids all mention of the fandango in his lengthy *Reglas útiles para los aficionados del danzar* of 1745, but he describes several stamping steps that would suit the fandango well: a simple traveling step called the *paso de canarios*, and the flashy *paso de Indias*.

Barretti describes the finger snapping of the dancers as a double snap using the thumb and middle finger but offers no details on castanet rhythms. In one edition of *Arte de danzar a la francesa* Minguet translates verbatim a rudimentary castanet notation invented by the Frenchman Raoul Auger Feuillet at the turn of the century (see figure 2). Its most surprising trait is the rolling of the castanets on the left hand and right hand, as well as on both hands, despite the absence of any instructions on how to roll. Whether Feuillet's system was really practiced in Spain – or even in France – is open to debate, for a mere half-century after Minguet's time, castanet technique resembled modern playing in every respect.

Figure 2

rarity until recently. New manuscripts are coming to light every year, and while we wait for this new evidence to be played and analyzed, we can signal certain points that relate specifically to dance.

First, nearly all sources describe the fandango as a rapid dance, though it may be that its infectious, driving rhythm created the illusion of velocity. Second, it was common for the composer or copyist to neglect writing out a final cadence. The intention was not to leave the dancers hanging in the air. Since the guitarist needed to keep playing as long as at least one couple was still dancing, he would certainly have brought the fandango to a finish at the appropriate moment. Finally, the instrumental fandango did not necessarily consist of symmetrical phrases, but often featured repeating motifs of unpredictable length: sometime eight or four measures, sometimes seven, five or only three. When performed at private assemblies and on street corners, the fandango must have been free and spontaneous, or even entirely improvised. The man and woman most likely responded to each other, and to the rhythms and emotions in the music, without attempting to execute identical step sequences.

In 1772-73 the English traveler Richard Twiss remarked upon the existence of *two* fandangos. The “gallant” fandango created a tableau of never-ending hedonism, while a “decent” fandango found its way into proper society. Joseph Townsend, another Englishman, decried the common fandango as “disgusting” when danced by the vulgar. The upper classes performed it in a different style, affecting a veneer of respectability – which made it all the more dangerous. Eventually the fandango was even considered chaste enough to figure in religious processions.

The first attempts to apply rules to the fandango no doubt helped set it on this course toward social respectability. According to legend, a certain Pedro de la Rosa came to Madrid in the 1740s equipped with a pedagogical method to teach the fandango. Whatever his rules may have been—and whether or not he really existed—the fandango was already practiced as a “school dance,” as it still is in the Escuela Bolera. The *fandangos antiguos* preserved in this school are slow and repetitive, belying their late-nineteenth-century origins, yet they may provide a distant link to the older “decent” fandangos. Twiss makes the surprising claim that all fandangos in Spain, whether “decent” or “gallant,” are based on the same melody, in 6/8.

Even Casanova’s voluptuous fandango was “respectable” in the sense that it was subject to rules and conventions, just like any ball dance of the time. Perfect decorum reigned in the ballroom. This was the Teatro de los Caños del Peral, used for public balls during Carnival, as was the better-known Teatro del Príncipe. The dancers, costumed as Turks, Harlequins, and the like, filled the boxes as well as the dance floor. The accompaniment was provided not by guitarists, but an orchestra. The Barcelona theater, for

example, boasted not one but two twenty- four-piece bands replete with strings, oboes, clarinets even trumpets. The musicians were divided into two groups so that one could rest while the other was playing.

According to Casanova the fandango was scheduled at a specific time, the second half of the evening, after ten o'clock. By then the minuets and contredanses were finished, and the dancers had had the chance to refresh themselves with biscuits, fruit and wine. The fandango did not simply start spontaneously; it was announced by a master of ceremonies. The couples did not fling themselves wildly into the dance; they arranged themselves in two orderly columns, one for men and one for women. A curious coincidence needs to be pointed out here. The double column was the hallmark of English country dances, which were quite popular at Spanish balls. This opens up new questions about the fandango's transformations.

On the surface, the country dance is the antithesis of the fandango. Repetitive, predictable and bound by strict geometrical rules, it encouraged polite social interaction among groups of four, eight, or sometimes many dozens of dancers. Yet it possessed a certain exhilarating power and invited flirtation. There were two types. The French variety was usually performed by four couples arranged in a closed square, called the *contradanza cerrada* or *contradanza de ocho* in Spanish. The English country dance, on the contrary, could accommodate an almost unlimited number of couples, with the men and the women facing each other in parallel lines. Outside England and its colonies this "longways" country dance rarely offered any serious competition to the French contredanse, with the noticeable exception of Spain, where it was known as the *contradanza inglesa* or *abierta* (see figure 5).

Dancing masters throughout Europe enlivened their country dances by incorporating elements of whatever couple dance was most fashionable at the moment: first the minuet, later the allemande, and finally the waltz. The fandango was not neglected. "La Miscelanea" is a *contradanza de ocho* known from collections published in Madrid, Barcelona and Valencia from the 1750s through the 1780s (see figure 3). The dance begins in the conventional French fashion but shifts to a "grand chain" danced to a seguidillas tune, then continues with a six-measure fandango during which the dancers return to their places in *pasos de fandango*. Interestingly, the ladies face in toward each other while the gentlemen are back-to-back to their partners, facing out (see figure 4). An early version by Minguet entitled "Los Presumidos y las Presumidas" has the dancers return to their places in the seguidillas and dance the fandango with their partner. This perhaps implies six measures of improvisation, or may be a step sequence so well-known that he saw no reason to describe it. Fandango steps are called for in another *contradanza* of the same period, "La Fandanguera." It begins with bows to one's partner and corner and continues with traveling *pasos de fandango* with the ladies and gentlemen back-to-back, as in "La Miscelanea." The triple-metre section in question is identified a "minuet."

- (7)
1. Los Caballeros, media Alameda. Con la señora de la izquierda, y otra con la compañera; 8. compare. Diferencia; 8. compare. =
2. Los Caballeros, toman de las manos à su compañeras, quedando ones al Centro donde hacen Balance, y Rigodon: Todos aviv à Derecha, y Rigodon, y de acazules 8. compare. Los Caballeros entran al Centro Como lo hicieron las señoras, ellas fueran, reviven el Balance, Rigodon, valse, y peaveor Rigodon; 8. compare. Cadena de seguidillas para el lugar opuesto, dirigen a ellas con la compañera, y desde allí reviven: todos à sus lugares en paso de fandango, los Caballeros de espalda, y las señoras de cara. =

2 La Miscelanea: de a ocho.

1 seguidilla.

Fandango.

Detailed description: This figure shows a musical score for a piece titled 'La Miscelanea: de a ocho'. It consists of three staves of music. The first staff is in treble clef with a 2/4 time signature. The second staff is in bass clef with a 2/4 time signature. The third staff is in bass clef with a 2/4 time signature and includes the instruction 'Fandango'. Above the third staff, there is a section labeled '1 seguidilla'.

Figure 3

(8)

Rueda de Todos; 8. Compare. =

(Música) Los Caballeros Conseria à su señora, y otra a la de la izquierda; y aviv con su compañera fuera al lugar opuesto 12. compare. A paso de fandango, entran à su sitio, los Caballeros de espalda, y las señoras de cara; y conclúese.

31 La Fandango: de a ocho.

tres veces.

Detailed description: This figure shows a musical score for a piece titled 'La Fandango: de a ocho'. It consists of three staves of music. The first staff is in treble clef with a 2/4 time signature. The second staff is in bass clef with a 2/4 time signature. The third staff is in bass clef with a 2/4 time signature and includes the instruction 'tres veces'.

Figure 4

London in the 1770s, whose title, “The Fandango” seems to be purely fanciful. Another questionable longways dance is “El Babau.” Found in the Eleanor Hague Manuscript at the Southwest Museum in Los Angeles, it is the work of a certain Joseph María García of Chalco, Mexico. The name “Babau” is perplexing, as is its subtitle, “fandango cathalan,” for the Catalans, unlike their neighbors in nearby Valencia, have never been particularly celebrated for their fandangos. At first glance its figures and 6/8 melody seem quite English, but this manuscript has not yet begun to yield all its secrets, and “El Babau” may well derive from a genuine Iberian source.

One longways fandango *contradanza* certainly performed in Spain is found in an anonymous collection at the Biblioteca Nacional de España, identified only by the owner’s name (“*Soy de don Balbino Serrano*”). The piece lacks choreography, but the music shows that it opens with a brief fandango of nine measures and then continues with a conventional gavotte-like tune. If it was danced in public balls it could have involved thirty or more couples, implying about thirty repetitions.

Figure 5

remains possible that it was nothing other than an English-style country dance consisting partly or wholly of a fandango melody, or even a longways reworking of *La Miscelanea*, which is known to have existed by the time of Casanova's stay and was performed *de ocho* in that very theater during the Carnival season of 1770.

Unfortunately, the *pasos de fandango* of these *contradanzas* were never described, but one striking detail does stand out: the motif of couples traveling back to back. It is possible that this formation also occurred in the fandango as performed by a single couple as it did in Carlo Blasis's *Manuel complet de la danse* of 1830. The male dancer's pose is very close to what Blasis calls an *arabesque*. It does not correspond to a modern balletic arabesque, but was so called because the dancer gestures with the same arm as leg, a characteristic supposedly inherited by the Spaniards from the Moors (see figure 6).

Figure 6

minuet that resulted in the birth of the *minué afandangado* (see figure 7). This was in the final decade of the eighteenth century, which also saw the appearance of the “strathspey minuet” in Scotland and even the “Congo minuet” in the Caribbean. The *minué fandango* inspired instrumental variations by various Romantic composers and was danced in theaters of Seville, Madrid and Barcelona. Outside Spain, it served as a final pas de deux in the ballet *Les Noces de Gamache*, which premiered at the Paris Opéra in 1801 with choreography by Louis Milon. Based loosely on Cervantes, it is the indirect forerunner of the familiar *Don Quixote* by Petipa and Gorsky. The critic Julien Geoffroy was disappointed by most of the ballet, but notes that the *menuet fandango* received much applause. He describes it as “a sort of Spanish minuet, much quicker and high-spirited than the ordinary minuet.”

Figure 7

Boleros de Millon

no. 23

pour faire la révérence on fait du C. P. la D. le droit. battement tendu derrière et devant avec la jambe de devant portez - à la 3^e passez l'autre par dessus pivotelle sur les pointes $\frac{3}{4}$ de tour seulement pour finir face à face coupé à droite révérence coupé à gauche idem jeté à droite pas de bourrée dessous, tous les deux en descendant coupé en arrière rapprochez devant. on répète le tout, la seconde fois lorsqu'on fait le pas de bourrée dessous tous les deux le foot à droite, le C. remonte à sa place et la D. descend vis-à-vis un peu dans l'ang. fin de la révérence. Le pied droit en bran à la 3^e les bras haut. 2 appels. Impried. Droit (ou pas de boleros) portez le droit derrière à la 1^{re} coupé à la 4^e pas de bourrée dessous et coupé en arrière, C. P. en revenant à ses places, encore pas de boleros portez les

Figure 8

century manuscript at the Paris Opéra. It originally served as a simple introduction to an elaborate bolero, and the choreography is by none other than Louis Milon (see figure 8). The two dancers point their feet behind, then before, pivot around three-quarters to face each other and bow twice, then travel downstage with a soft *jeté* and *pas de bourrée* and repeat the whole sequence, for a total of sixteen measures. The brief but precious fragment is found among the notebooks of Léon Michel, who is remembered as the father of Arthur Saint-Léon. The latter also choreographed a ballet entitled *Le Procès du fandango* at Vienna's Kärntnertheater in 1858, with music by Pugnî. It was inspired by the now-old story of the “trial” of the fandango.

A costume sketch at the Musée Carnavalet in Paris depicts a French comedy based on that story, shedding light on how the French performed the fandango in the early 1800s. A lively young widow and her Spanish dancing master are pictured in the middle of a fandango, rising high onto the ball of one foot and extending one arm well over the head.

They seem to be holding each other at the wrist, an un-Spanish detail, especially considering that they are using castanets (see figure 9).

Figure 9

the musical structure of the seguidillas, specifically the *seguidillas boleras* or bolero, the most popular dance of the time. The word “seguidillas” implies a sequence, namely the alternation of verse and chorus, also known as *copla* and *estribillo*, terms stemming from vocal music but also applied to instrumental dances. The *copla-estribillo* structure is so familiar that it is often assumed to date from the very dawn of time, but in the case of the fandango the change appears to be relatively recent. By the 1770s vocal fandangos with *copla* and *estribillo* coexisted with seguidillas in various theatrical works, and by the 1790s we find an instrumental fandango intended for social dance, bearing the enigmatic title “Fandango aleore,” from an anonymous late-eighteenth-century manuscript at the Biblioteca Nacional (see figure 10). From this point on the fandango was more formal and predictable, unlike the earliest examples, where a short melody was repeated *ad infinitum* until the dancers dropped from fatigue, or the somewhat rambling free-form instrumental pieces of the next generations.

Figure 10

this period thanks to Antonio Cairón’s *Compendio de las principales reglas del baile* of 1820. The author was a professional specializing in the bolero, which in his view is, “to a degree, an imitation of the fandango.” In fact, a bilateral exchange existed between the two. The fandango freely adapted step combinations from the aerial bolero, taking care to perform them gracefully and close to the ground, often with the effect of sliding or gliding. Thus, the change in musical structure was accompanied by a dramatic abandonment of the famous “bold leaps” of the previous century. Nevertheless, the music retained a quick

tempo, as well as the old custom of dancing for as long as the dancers wished.

The “Fandango aleore” begins with a short *entrada* leading into the *paseo*, better known today as a *pasada*, which corresponds to the *estribillo* music. This step is documented by Cairón as an open *pas de bourrée* beginning with a stamp of the foot and continuing with a turn in place to put the dancers face to face. After each *paseo* the dancers perform a relatively long *mudanza* or *diferencia*.

In addition to the bolero steps described by Cairón there are still others documented in a satirical work published in Philadelphia in 1807, *Bolerología*. These include *matalaraña* (a gliding to the side with a stamp, as if to kill an imaginary spider), *taconeo* (perhaps a specific step rather than a whole category of beaten footwork) and *avance con retirada* (advancing and retreating, mentioned by Beaumarchais). The composer Fernando Sor, who was married to a French ballerina, tells us that the basic *paseo de bolero* was essentially a variant of the familiar opening step from Sevillanas.

Crotalogía, a satirical work of 1792 that presents itself as a treatise on castanets, confirms that castanets of this period had two pitches, deeper for the left hand and higher for the right. Rolls were executed on the right hand exclusively, as they are today. Beats were rarely if ever performed on both hands at once, and the *choque* or crash of the castanets was avoided, at least in the bolero. The most typical rhythm cited is the two-measure phrase *ririrá-ririrá-ririrá-ririrá-ti-tá-ti-tá*. This rhythm does not conform to that of surviving boleros but lends itself to the fandango.

In this period we also find the earliest depictions of the fandango, beginning with an illustration from Christian August Fischer’s *Voyage en Espagne* from the late 1790s, where the dancing couple, normally face to face, is depicted facing the viewer (see figure 11). We see both dancers inclining slightly back and opposing the pointed left foot with an arm gesture over the head. A pointing of the foot is often found in Spanish classical and regional dances, as well as in the *minué afandangado*, not to mention Spanish entrées of the Baroque age. The left arm is held out to the side, and the lady holds one corner of her apron.

Figure 11

he makes the first timid attempt to describe one: the arms were generally held out away from the body, sometimes with the elbow slightly bent, and they were constantly raised and lowered during the dance. This description, summary as it is, seems to correspond to Fischer's engraving and to Cairón's rules.

An engraving from about 1810 by Pierre Chasselat shows two arm positions: one couple holds their arms high in the general stance for popular dances, but with the hands pronated, while another couple curls one hand over the shoulder, crossing the other in front of the chest. This over-the-shoulder position was also employed in the bolero. But the most characteristic *port de bras* of the early bolero was a diagonal arm position, which is ironically never used in the Escuela Bolera. Considering the constant cross-pollination between the fandango and the bolero at this time, diagonal arms are very likely to have been used in the fandango as well.

the fandango, which occurred in the United States in the last years of the eighteenth century. Music publishers furnished “fandangos” to amateur musicians of Boston, New York and Philadelphia from the 1790s well into the nineteenth century. Not surprisingly, they grew more and more waltz-like with each decade. Among the earlier examples we find an undated romantic reverie which in fact is nothing other than the 6/8 fandango that Richard Twiss had claimed in the 1770s to be the basic fandango performed throughout Spain. The American version was published in Baltimore sometime before 1797 by the English-born composer Benjamin Carr, who fleshed it out as a rondo (see figure 12).

Figure 12

the American stage seem to have originated in London. A “signor Cortez” is known to have been demonstrating the “Spanish hornpipe” and other dances in American towns, but it is feared that this was a stage name affected for the occasion by an actor of the time, “Mister Curtiss, of London.” A touring production of *Don Juan* from the 1780s, thought to have included Gluck’s famous fandango, gives every sign of being based on a London version of Gasparo Angiolini’s ballet *Don Juan*, adapted by Charles Le Picq. In a 1795 revival the child prodigy Louis Duport performed a fandango “with variations,” which

suggests that a local musician furnished the music. *The Mountaineers*, a comedy with music by Samuel Arnold, was also performed in American towns. Advertisements in American newspapers specify that the concluding “Spanish feast,” danced by Andalusian goatherds, was performed “with Castinets.”

Gil Blas, or The Cave of the Robbers was a comical pantomime ballet performed in New York and other towns on the East Coast by Monsieur Francisquy, a former dancer of the Paris Opéra and the Grand Théâtre of Bordeaux (see figure 13). Monsieur Francisquy’s Parisian training and stage experience were certainly on a high level, but nothing indicates that he had any direct knowledge of Spanish dance or that he had traveled to Spain. He did, however, spend several years in the French colony of Saint-Domingue, modern Haiti. This is pertinent, because it was at this very period that French writers began drawing comparisons between the fandango and Afro-Caribbean dances, to the point that Moreau de Saint-Méry, another refugee from Saint-Domingue to the United States, claimed that the fandango was nothing more than another name for La Chica, a Caribbean dance of seduction in which the woman entices her partner in a sort of erotic pantomime, expressing coquetry, tenderness, fright, hope and other emotions. The music furnished by the Franco-American composer Victor Pelissier, on the contrary, could not have been more European. Written in 3/8 with hemiolas, it resembles nothing more than a *passepied*, a Breton folk dance that became popular at the court of Louis XIV.

Figure 13

tropical touches it may have helped bring the fandango back to its roots, reintroducing the soft arm gestures and pelvic movements that had so astonished Father Martí in Cádiz. Lovers of old New York will be interested to learn that it was performed at the old Park Theater, within sight of City Hall and Saint Paul's Chapel in downtown Manhattan (see figure 14). Theater Alley long remained as a souvenir, but this final vestige of early American theater, and of the fandango's brief New York adventure, has sadly disappeared from view.

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